

SPACE SAMPLING TECHNIQUES COMPARISON FOR A SYNTHETIC LOW-PASS FILTER BAYESIAN NEURAL NETWORK

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Abstract— This paper presents a comparative analysis of three sampling space points generation techniques for developing a Bayesian neural network (BNN) surrogate model of a synthetic second-order low-pass filter. The objective is to assess the effectiveness and efficiency of different sampling methods in the performance of the Bayesian surrogate model. The study takes inspiration from widely used sampling methods such as uniform distribution, uniformly distributed random numbers, and Latin Hypercube Sampling (LHS). Corresponding results show that in the overall performance, the BNN surrogate models trained with the LHS sampling method are the best while the worst model is achieved when using the uniform distribution.

Keywords— *Artificial neural networks, Bayesian, low-pass filter, latin hypercube sampling, uniform distribution, uniformly distributed random numbers, DoE.*

I. INTRODUCTION

Bayesian neural networks (BNNs) are relevant for developing surrogate models since they can provide point estimates and probabilistic predictions. Some of the most important characteristics of BNNs are uncertainty quantification, robustness to noisy data, regularization, prior knowledge incorporation, sequential learning and the ability to handle limited data [1]-[3]. Related to high frequency circuits, BNNs has been applied to the design of amplifiers, filters, transceivers, radar systems, mems, as well as for circuits optimization [4]-[6].

The relevance of sampling methods for developing surrogate models lies in their crucial role in constructing accurate and reliable approximations of complex models with fewer computational resources. Surrogate models, also known as metamodels, are mathematical representations created using a limited set of data points obtained by evaluating the original model at specific input locations. Some key features of sampling methods for developing surrogate models are efficient model approximation, cost reduction, global and local approximation, sensitivity analysis and exploration of high dimensional input spaces [7], [8]. Some relevant techniques for sampling space include Latin Hypercube Sampling (LHS), uniform design, quasi-Monte Carlo sampling, orthogonal arrays, Sobol sequences, Halton sequences, and random sampling [8]. In this work we compare the performance of BNNs surrogate models developed using LHS, uniform design, and random sampling.

The choice of sampling technique depends on the characteristics of the problem, the dimensionality of the input space, and the resources available. In many cases, LHS and uniform distributed sampling are preferred due to their ability to provide a more uniform and efficient coverage of the input space, resulting in more accurate and reliable surrogate models. However, for certain simple problems or initial exploration, random uniformly distributed points generation can be a reasonable choice [9].

This work aims to compare the performance of BNN surrogate models for a synthetic second order low pass filter using the three previously described sampling techniques. The work is organized as follows: Section I gives a brief introduction to sampling space techniques, Section II describes the steps to develop the surrogate model, Section III shows the corresponding results, and finally some conclusions of this work are presented.

II. SYNTHETIC LOW-PASS FILTER SURROGATE MODEL

For developing the surrogate model of the low-pass filter, we followed a series of steps. First, we define an initial design for the circuit which is used as the center of the design space. Second, we obtain the learning base points which are used for training the surrogate model. These points are obtained using the space sampling techniques within the region of interest. As a third step, we train the surrogate models, in this case, using the BNN. Finally, we measure the surrogate model performance by using a set of random testing points.

A. Synthetic Low-Pass Filter Circuit

The synthetic circuit consist of a simple second order low-pass filter which employs only a capacitor, C , and an inductor, L . For the initial design, component values are defined as $L = 11.254$ nH and $C = 4.5015$ pF. A frequency sweep from 0.1 GHz to 4 GHz with 31 frequency points is used.

B. Sampling Design Space

For generating the different sampling designs a Matlab script was generated. The code begins by specifying the center values for L and C and a size for the design region. For this work, the center values correspond to the initial design with a design region size of +/- 10%.

For the uniform distribution, 11 values were set for L and C , which corresponds to 5 values from the upper limit to the center, 5 points from the lower limit to the center, and 1 point for the

center of the design region. Each possible combination of L and C is simulated resulting in 121 sampling points.

For the uniformly distributed random points, the Matlab function *rand* was used. We set the lower limit as $\text{low_lim} = [0.9*L, 0.9*C]$ and the upper limit as $\text{up_lim} = [1.1*L, 1.1*C]$. 121 random points between those limits were generated.

For the LHS design, we used the Matlab function *lhsdesign*, with the same previously defined upper and lower limits, and generating also 121 sampling points.

For the uniform distribution there is only one possible sampling space points distribution but for the case of the random and LHS distributions we get different sampling space points each time the Matlab code is compiled. To avoid a bias in the performance results, we generate 10 sets of sampling space points for the random and LHS distributions, respectively. Resulting space points are shown in Fig. 1.

C. Bayesian ANN Surrogate Model

In this work, a multilayer perceptron (MLP) neural network, specifically a 3-layer perceptron (3LP), was implemented. The network topology is defined by the number of inputs, hidden neurons, and outputs [10]. The ANN was implemented in Matlab using the neural network toolbox with the Bayesian regularization as the training algorithm. The training data was divided into three subsets: 80% for training, 10% for validation, and 10% for testing. The number of hidden neurons was set using the procedure in [11], by identifying the point where the testing error no longer improves relative to the training error. For measuring the ANN performance, we calculate the mean square error (MSE), by obtaining the mean of the differences power by 2 between the ANN and the circuit response.

III. SURROGATE MODELS PERFORMANCE RESULTS

To measure the generalization performance of the 21 corresponding surrogate models, we simulate 1000 random points inside the design region (see Fig. 2). The MSE for each surrogate model at learning and testing points as well as the final number of neurons for each training set are shown in Table I.

From the corresponding surrogate model results, it is seen that the worst generalization performance is achieved when training using the uniform distribution. The best generalization performance is achieved by a set of random distribution. However, if we take into consideration the top 5 performance models, 4 of them correspond to sets of LHS designs.

Analyzing the number of hidden neurons, for resulting BNNs using the random distribution, the maximum number of hidden neurons is 79 and the minimum is 23, having a standard deviation of 18.3. For the BNNs using LHS, the maximum number is 57 and the minimum is 29, having a standard deviation of 9.4. So, the complexity of the neural network tends to be more homogeneous when using LHS distributions rather than using random points.

Fig. 1. Resulting learning base points using: a) uniform distribution, b) random distribution, and c) LHS design. For random and LHS designs, set 1 of 10 is shown.

Fig. 2. Corresponding 10,000 testing base points generated using a random distribution within the design region.

TABLE I. BNNs PERFORMANCE SORTED FROM THE BEST TO WORST TESTING MSE (GENERALIZATION PERFORMANCE)

Sampling Technique	Testing MSE	Learning MSE	Neurons
random set 1	3.53E-11	9.55E-03	30
LHS set 5	2.44E-10	8.26E-03	57
LHS set 1	2.48E-10	9.59E-03	31
LHS set 2	2.72E-10	7.47E-03	40
LHS set 9	2.79E-10	5.81E-03	51
random set 4	4.26E-10	8.52E-03	60
LHS set 4	5.86E-10	9.53E-03	29
random set 9	5.96E-10	6.71E-03	23
LHS set 3	6.30E-10	7.75E-03	42
random set 3	6.81E-10	8.48E-03	44
random set 6	1.03E-09	6.33E-03	41
LHS set 7	1.08E-09	8.24E-03	40
random set 1	1.28E-09	4.17E-02	35
random set 10	1.42E-09	5.93E-03	79
random set 5	1.46E-09	8.55E-03	35
LHS set 6	1.73E-09	7.44E-03	44
random set 8	1.74E-09	6.55E-03	68
LHS set 10	2.50E-09	9.98E-03	34
LHS set 8	2.88E-09	9.88E-03	53
random set 7	4.50E-09	7.99E-03	32
uniform distribution	1.83E-08	1.69E-01	8

CONCLUSIONS

In this work, a comparison between three sampling design techniques (uniform distribution, uniform distributed random points, and LHS design) was done. The purpose was to identify the best sampling technique for developing a Bayesian ANN of a synthetic second order low pass filter. To train the ANNs, 121 learning points were generated. 1 set for the uniform distribution, 10 sets for the random distribution, and 10 sets for the LHS design. The number of hidden neurons was selected as the point where the testing error does not improve respect to the training error. To test the generalization performance, the MSE was calculated for 1000 random testing points. Corresponding results showed that the worst performance was achieved by using the uniform distribution while 4 of the 5 best generalization performances were achieved by using the LHS design distribution. Also, the corresponding ANN hidden neurons when using LHS designs tends to be more homogeneous than those using random points. According to these results, we suggest the usage of LHS design distribution for developing Bayesian ANN of synthetic HF circuits.

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